

Exploring the effects of Covid-19 on young adult identity formation: A qualitative study of university students, emerging from adolescence, using in-depth interviews.

Jirayus Macuga

Declaration

I hereby declare that the Research Report submitted for the Psychology Honours degree to the Independent Institute of Education is my own work and has not previously been submitted to another university or higher education institution for degree purposes.

Signed: J.Macuga

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ABSTRACT

In 2020 the Covid-19 pandemic first hit, and people's lives were put on hold as South Africa first entered lockdown and social distancing was put in place. As these social restrictions became the new norm, many young South African adults and students were stuck indoors during a time in their lives when socialisation and meeting people is paramount to development. However, due to the how quickly Covid-19 came and how quickly the world has had to adjust to it, there isn't much research done on how Covid-19 impacted young adult identity formation. This proposed research study aims to explore how Covid-19 and the social restrictions that took place has impacted young adults' identity formation. Five participants were chosen using convenience sampling and underwent in-depth interviews in order to find out the experiences of young adults during Covid-19 and how it has affected them post lockdown. The data gathered was qualitative in nature, and thematic analysis used to interpret the findings. Covid-19 and lockdown were found to have negative experiences during the initial lockdown, but development and identity post lockdown when society opened again were found to have benefitted from Covid-19 and social distancing.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Contextualisation

In 2020 the world was hit by a global pandemic known as Covid-19. As a countermeasure to stop the spread of Covid-19, South Africa along with the world underwent a hard lockdown, that brought along social changes such as social distancing, the wearing of masks and quarantine in your own home. While the social world stopped, people cannot stop developing and growing and thus many groups of people in varying ages underwent important developmental milestones during a hard lockdown. The focus of this research is age group of young adults in South Africa, who currently undergoing the stage of identity formation. Identity formation is an integral in an individual finding themselves and being able to function in a civil society (Erikson, 1950; Marcia, 1993). As shown by research and theories conducted by Erikson and Marcia, the stagnation or failure to reach a developmental stage (identity) can lead to further complications in pursuing relationships, careers and for overall life fulfilment (1950; 1993). This research aims to explore whether or not South African young adults managed to adequately form an identity despite Covid-19 and the social restrictions take took place.

1.2. Rationale

1.2.1. *Personal rationale*

The development of personality has always been of great interest to me personally, personality is such a multi-layered domain of people which makes everyone so unique and being able to understand how and why some people share certain personality traits is an aspect of psychology that has always been fascinating.

1.2.2. *Academic rationale*

Covid-19 has devastated the world and influenced nearly every aspect of life in one way or another. In addition to the effects the actual virus has caused, social life as people have known for several years has been disrupted greatly and to a worldwide scale. Prior to Covid-19 activities such as schooling and work were done by going

into schools and offices/workplaces, following the outbreak of Covid-19 these activities have transitioned to mostly online learning and remote work. Social disruptions and restrictions such as lockdown, wearing of masks, social distancing and online learning/work have been the major social impacts caused by Covid-19 (Young, 2020). These disruptions have impacted society in several ways, this research will investigate how psychological development was impacted within young adults.

1.2.3. Relevance of research to the field of psychology

Psychosocial development and identity formation are two theories within psychology which have been researched and spoken about extensively over the last 70 years (Erikson, 1950). While there is a lot of theory to understanding identity formation and how it develops, it is important to revise and compare research of identity formation so it can be discovered how Covid-19 has impacted identity formation. The maldevelopment of identity leads to a state of identity crisis, where an individual cannot identify or commit to an identity, individuals with identity confusion lack the formation of the virtue of fidelity, which negatively impacts interaction with others and the social world (Erikson, 1950). Furthermore it has been pointed out by Scott (2020) that Covid-19 and the social restrictions caused by Covid-19 has had a negative impact on the mental health of South Africans, this research will be used to understand the current mental health state of young adults.

1.3. Problem Statement

Identity formation is an important aspect of our psychosocial development (Erikson, 1950). Covid-19 and the social restrictions that were put in the place has impacted all aspects of life, affecting people's social and economic lives amongst others. However, the impact of the development of identity formation during a global pandemic such as Covid-19 is a facet of personality development that has not been looked at. The development of adolescence identity formation is an aspect of

personal development which has been affected but in unknown ways, these effects that were brought on because of the social disruptions caused by Covid-19 need to be understood so development of people during Covid-19 can be understood as a whole.

1.4. Purpose Statement

The aim of this research is to find out how Covid-19, specifically the social disruptions such as wearing of masks, social distancing, lockdown and online learning has affected young adult identity formation.

1.5. Research Question

How has Covid 19 and its social disruptions affected young adult identity formation?

How has social distancing, online learning and lockdown affected the development of young adult identity formation?

1.6. Objectives

Objectives of this research is to explore how the social disruptions caused by Covid19 has affected the development of young adult identity formation. Additionally the research aims to find out whether young adults felt that they managed to adequately achieve identity formation despite the difficulties that Covid-19 and it's social restrictions brought into their lives.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical foundation

Two theories will be used as the major theories that will lay the groundwork as the theoretical foundation. Identity Status theory by Marcia (1993) and Erikson's (1950) Psychosocial Development theory, specifically the stage of identity vs role confusion, Stage 5.

2.1.1. Theory 1: Psychosocial development Theory

Erikson's (1950) psychosocial theory of development built on the works first set out by Freud (date). Both Freud and Erikson notion that development is majorly influenced by childhood and its experiences, and Erikson expanded upon this by incorporating that social dynamics is also a key component of development (Orenstein & Lewis, 2021). Erikson's (1950) model of psychosocial development proposes that human development takes place in invariable eight stages that take place throughout childhood, adolescence and adulthood and is influenced by biological, social and psychological factors. Each of the eight stages that Erikson laid out are defined by two alternative psychological inclinations. The various stages are as follows; First stage: Trust vs. mistrust, Second stage: Autonomy vs. Shame and doubt, Third stage: Initiative vs guilt, Fourth stage: Industry vs. inferiority, Fifth stage: Identity vs. role confusion, Sixth stage: Intimacy vs. isolation, Seventh stage: Generativity vs. stagnation, Eighth stage: Integrity vs. despair (Erikson, 1950). This research will make use of the fifth stage of development, namely: identity vs. role confusion, the fifth stage posits that between the ages of 12 and 18 adolescents are tasked with finding and understanding their identity. The two psychological alternatives of the identity vs. role confusion stage are to either establish the formation of an identity (positive) or the enduring of role confusion (negative). These alternatives which, according to Erikson (1950), most adolescents will find themselves in at some point, have a major influence on how individuals develop and interact in the future. Individuals who find and understand their identity will have a

stronger sense of self and a decreased level of anxiety when interacting with the outer world (Orenstein & Lewis, 2021).

Erikson's theory has been chosen, with emphasis on the fifth stage of identity vs. role confusion, to provide the framework as to how we understand young adult identity formation. Particularly because this theory and its aforementioned stage focuses on society and its influences on how personality is developed, and is needed to understand the effects of socio-environmental changes on the development of identity. Erikson's psychosocial development theory (1950) also has its limitations, as when speaking about identity formation Erikson developmental model assumes that one's formation of identity is done in a normative environment with normative functioning (Cote, 2018), not taking into consideration extreme cases such as the Covid-19 pandemic for example. Stage five of the psychosocial development theory is defined by how the individual develops a personality and what sort of roles society has for them or that society expects of them. The Covid-19 pandemic and the social restrictions put in place due to the pandemic has stopped young adults from planning their futures, leaving them feeling uncertain and arrested in their development, anxious and depressed (Gittings et al., 2021).

Although Erikson's (1950) theory has been used as the foundation over the years to understand development, the theory itself is somewhat dated and not extensive enough to provide a holistic description of identity formation. Research conducted by Samsonovich (2021) using empirical research to test the validity of Erikson's stages of psychosocial development in the 21st century, the research indicated moderate validity with mixed results. Qualitative studies suggest that Erikson's (1950) theory on identity crisis still holds prevalence today and the identity crisis which young adults are facing today is linked to the high numbers of young adults, especially those who are students as well, who are seeking mental health treatments and advisors (Cote, 2018).

2.1.2. Theory 2: Identity Status Theory

Identity status theory, proposed by Marcia (1993) is an expansion and refinement on the work done by Erikson (1950) on psychosocial development. This theory is compatible with the psychosocial theory discussed above, however, it provides a distinct view on the development of identity which views identity as a global construct

(Waterman, 1988). Marcia (1993) primarily expanded Erikson's (1950) work by focusing on adolescent development and the formation of identity. Marcia expands on these thoughts and says that identity is only formed through how much control and input an individual has over their life (Marcia, 1993). This theory works well when looking at how Covid-19 and social restrictions affected identity formation as many young adults and people have felt that a lot of their freedom and choice has been taken away due to Covid-19 (Young, 2020). Identity status theory set the notion that adolescent development is not defined necessarily by identity formation or identity confusion but rather that identity is formed by how much control one has in exploring and committing to roles in various different life aspects, such as religion, gender roles and relationship choices (Marcia, 1993). Within the development of identity formation, Marcia (1993) laid out four general stages which are used to signify where an individual is in terms of developing an identity; these stages are characterised by varying degrees of anxiety or crises, and identity formulation. These four stages are namely, (1) Identity diffusion – adolescents have no sense of having choices, he/she is not willing or has not made a commitment yet, (2) Identity foreclosure – which refers to the adolescents willingness to commit some roles or goals for the future however having not experienced anxiety or pressure relating to this commitment, (3) Identity moratorium – which describes the adolescents currently engaging with their state of crisis, to explore various commitments, interest and roles which are being explored but have not been finalized and (4) Identity achievement - adolescents has gone through an identity crisis and had made a commitment to a sense of identity (Marcia, 1993).

This research will focus on the latter three stages that Marcia has identified. Namely identity foreclosure, identity moratorium and identity achievement (Marcia, 1993).

Identity foreclosure to see whether adolescents were ready to commit to roles/identity prior or during the pandemic. Identity moratorium, since this stage looks at adolescents currently in crisis, this stage will be used to determine what type of crisis and the severity of the crisis that the adolescents were enduring. Identity achievement, to determine whether identity had been able to be achieved during the pandemic or what the effects are of trying to achieve an identity amidst the current problems surrounding the pandemic.

2.2. Review of previous literature

Previous literature that was used focused on the works of Erikson and Marcia (1950; 1966, 1987, 1993, 2006) using these theories and studies the theoretical foundation was founded. Theme 1 of “Identity Crisis” focused on the works of Erikson and Marcia regarding identity crisis, but with reference to more modern studies on identity. The next two themes of “Effects of Social Exclusion” and “Covid-19 in South Africa”, were founded by researching journal articles that focused on the respective themes.

2.2.1. Theme 1: Identity Crisis

Marcia (1966, 1987, 1993, 2006) took the works of Erikson and the psychosocial development theory and further refined it, specifically the stage of adolescent identity formation. Marcia believed, just like Erikson, that the formation of identity is a multi-stage process that takes place over a number of years and are influenced by a variety of biological, economical, psychological and social factors. When looking into

Erikson’s theory and stage 5 of identity development, Marcia takes the model by Erikson and expands upon it to include different stages within the stage of identity formation. Marcia’s theory of identity status theory will be used to build upon the work of Erikson and expand on it, as Marcia is able to describe what place within identity formation an individual is currently in. The major differences within the works of Erikson (1950) and the work laid out by Marcia (1993), is that within Erikson’s theory there are two outcomes which is meant to cover/explain the process that all individuals would go through. Erikson claims that during stage five, which would start at age 12 till roughly age 18, that individuals would have either found an identity

(identity formation) or have not yet (identity confusion), identity confusion would result in an identity crisis.

Erikson believes that identity crisis is a psychological state which stems from the absence or the maldevelopment of an identity. Marcia believes that crisis is essential for identity to be achieved and is an integral part of one's development, crisis is needed to re-evaluate one's choices and values, and it is through this crisis a commitment is made to a specific role (Marcia, 1993). These theories on the formation of identity and identity crisis have been backed up by studies conducted by Cote (2018) and Samsonovich (2021). The article "*The enduring usefulness of Erikson's concept on identity crisis in the 21st century: An analysis of student mental health concerns*" states that the model of understanding identity and identity crisis laid out by Erikson and Marcia are still the foundations in understanding identity formation today (Cote, 2018). Using a combination of the works by Erikson and Marcia, this research will hope to shed light on whether the social restrictions have had an impact on identity formation, and whether the Covid-19 pandemic and the said restrictions were at all influential in developing identity and to the commitment of roles. The Covid-19 pandemic and social restrictions are indeed the crisis that will be at the forefront of the development of identity, but it is how it affected identity formation which is unknown.

2.2.2. Theme 2: Effects of social deprivation and exclusion

Social deprivation and exclusion is an experience that not many people thought anything of until the hard lockdown of the Covid-19 pandemic. Now due to social restrictions people are forced to isolate and in return they are being socially deprived and excluded which has a number of effects on human development and personality. Studies done by Seidel et al. (2013) on the effects on social exclusion showed that social exclusion would lead to lower levels in positive mood ratings and an increase in the mood ratings of anger. This is proof that social exclusion does have a negative effect on the wellbeing of an individual, affecting their anger when one is socially excluded and vice versa there is a decrease in sadness levels when one is socially included (Seidel et al., 2013). It has also been found that social

deprivation in childhood is linked with decreased ventral striatum activation (Hein et al., 2020), this means that social deprivation is linked to decreased brain activity which plays a role in an individual's mood and learning ability. However at adolescent age, the brain and one's personality and identity is still being formed as well. This research will build on the fact that social deprivation decreased ventral striatum activity and explore whether social deprivation will also lower the activity of the ventral striatum within adolescent individuals.

Lack of strong and quality relationships with others is a risk factor for major depression (Teo et al, 2013). The social distancing and lockdown that Covid-19 brought along could be a contributing factor towards regression of mental wellbeing and the possible diagnosis of major depression. Studies done in South Africa on depression in people has shown an increase in people displaying depressive symptoms since the start of the Covid-19 lockdown (Scott, 2020). Studies done by Kroger et al, has also provided support for Erikson's (1968) and Marcia's (1993) notion that individuals who undergo identity status transitions during late adolescence or young adulthood, are more than twice as likely to undergo progressive change rather than regressive change. Erikson (1968) believed that adolescence is the period in which identity formation becomes the main concern of an individual, and identity is partly formed through the social connections people make. Social distancing and lockdown would take away an individual's ability to form and maintain relationships possibly causing role confusion. Role confusion can cause people to doubt their meaning and purpose of existence, leading to sense of loss and confusion within (Sokol, 2009).

Adolescents are at an unique age where the social environment plays an important role in the creation of one's self-identity, for functioning of brain activity and for general mental health (Orben et al., 2020). While social deprivation during Covid-19 was helped by technology and being able to digitally connect with friends and family, a period of even a few months could have huge implications as to how the adolescents have developed socially and developed their identity (Orben et al., 2020). To add to this, almost all studies done on social exclusion and deprivation has been completed in controlled environments where exclusion was forced and being

tested. In regards to this research social deprivation is a phenomenon that all South Africans had to endure rather unexpectedly. Social deprivation has also never been researched to this extent, where isolation took place for months at a time and with external factors such as school, economic pressures and loss of public events was also affecting everyone (Orden et al., 2020).

2.2.3. Theme 3: Effects of the Covid-19 pandemic in South Africa

Covid-19 has had several effects on the South African people, economy and society. From the economy hitting a standstill due to lack of economic moves being made, this resulted from the lockdown and stopping of work that many citizens faced. Many small businesses were forced to close down, job losses in almost every industry but the biggest impact that Covid-19 had on the economy was how the leisure and tourism industry was severely affected (Young, 2020). Observations done by the study by Young (2020) highlights just how the people of South Africa had to cope with the lockdown and what type of recreational activities were available for those living during the height of the pandemic. Most forms of social interaction were not allowed so families and individuals had to turn to more domestic activities and spent more time with family (Young, 2020). Young also points out how most tasks such as school and work were done online now, this goes even further as many South Africans would have virtual braai nights in order to spend time with others where it wasn't allowed. This highlights the importance of social interaction amongst people, and while it was difficult for everyone. It is especially interesting to be able to research and determine how identity formation has been affected as the need to develop through social interaction is most prevalent during adolescents.

The isolation and quarantine that everyone has had to experience would play an important role in understanding how identity formation has been affected. Isolation and quarantine due to others or yourself having Covid-19 has had negative impacts on the South African population, there have been articles and discussions regarding whether the lockdown imposed by the South African government was a measure that

was needed or simply just a draconian power play (Moodley et al, 2020). While the legal status of the lockdown will not be discussed here, it raises interesting points as to whether the lockdown was necessary and ethical for the country. Mental health is the last facet that will be looked at, as it is proven in South Africa that Covid-19 and everything that came with it has had a negative impact on the mental health of the South African people (Scott, 2020). Scott's (2020) research focuses on the mental health of occupational therapists and what occupational therapists can do to help others, but there are statistics as well which highlight just how South African people were affected. Prior to Covid-19, 16.5% of South Africans experience common mental health problems, while after Covid-19, 34% and 35% of South Africans reported feeling depressed and lonely respectively (Scott, 2020). Since it is known just how badly the South African population has been affected, these statistics will be used to determine whether university student's mental health is in the same sort of state and just how their mental health has affected the development of identity formation.

Covid-19 has also affected the academic field and careers of young adults countrywide. South Africa had to enter a sudden lockdown which was accompanied by the first attempt at a fully online schooling system. This would affect the young adults experiences of school, as online learning requires a learner to be able to make meaningful connection with the digital work, as well as maintain multimodal communications (Chiu et al, 2021).

To conclude, the above themes were identified as the aspects that needed to be explored for the research. First theme "Identity Crisis" to understand what is an identity crisis and what leads to it. Theme two "Effects of Social Exclusion" was explored to understand how individuals who are socially excluded respond and how it affects them. Theme 3 "Effects of Covid-19 in South Africa" to understand the type of environment South African young adults found themselves in and how the environment and social factors affected the population.

2.3. Conceptualisation (and operationalisation)

Adolescence: the period of life between childhood and adulthood, between the ages of 13 and 19 (Erikson, 1950).

Anxiety: a psychological state of persistent worry or fear to do with the self and self-identity (Erikson, 1950).

Identity - the individual's sense of self, defined by physical, psychological and social characteristics which are subjective to every individual. Can also be shaped by roles the individual has in society (APA, 2002)

Identity achievement: achievement of identity through a process of exploration and strong commitment to beliefs, values or goals (Marcia, 1993)

Identity confusion – a psychological state in which there is a split in the self-image and identity of the individual (Erikson, 1968).

Identity crisis – a psychological state in which the individual is going through hardship which results in the questioning of maldevelopment of an identity.

Identity diffusion: period of development where youth have not committed nor explored a particular identity (Marcia, 1993)

Identity foreclosure: period of development where adolescents are not actively exploring what's important to them (Marcia, 1993)

Identity formation – the process in which the development of identity is accomplished. This research will focus on the identity formation of adolescents specifically.

Identity moratorium: period of development where adolescents are in a 'crisis' and is experimenting with different views, beliefs and goals (Marcia, 1993)

Psychosocial development – how an individual develops psychologically with the needs and demands of society (Erikson, 1950)

Social restrictions – rules and regulations that were set by the SA government to combat the spread of Covid-19. In this document social restrictions will specifically be used as a blanket term for the following restrictions; lockdown, social distancing, online learning and wearing of masks.

Young adult: a person between the ages of 20 and 39 (Erikson, 1950)

3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHDOLOGY

3.1. Outline of worldview/paradigm/tradition

This research falls into an interpretivist paradigm. Interpretivist paradigms focus on gaining in-depth meaning and understanding of a phenomenon, considering subjectivity and relativism (Creswell et al, 2014). Interpretivism will be used in order to gain an understanding of the adolescents while considering their unique perspectives and experiences. The ontological position of interpretivism is relativism, relativism is the approach that states that reality is subjective and therefore will differ from person to person (Scotland, 2012). This aligns with the researchers intended method of research as the researcher will interpret the subjective experiences every participants had of Covid-19 and the social restrictions. The epistemological view of interpretivism is that the researcher is a part of the research itself, and therefore can never be fully objective or removed from the research. Lastly, the axiological position of interpretivism is that research is value bound, and the researcher will be subjective due to being part of the research (Scotland, 2012).

3.2. Research approach and design

The research conducted is one of a qualitative nature. Qualitative will be used in order to accommodate and take findings from different perspectives. The research will be exploratory in nature as well, as it looks to explore what the effects of Covid 19's social disruptions had on identity formation. Exploratory was chosen so that the subjective experiences that individuals had during Covid-19 could be interpreted. Exploratory research is used when there is little knowledge about a subject, to signal out variables and key issues and to obtain a deeper understanding of the topic

(Creswell et al., 2014). Due to the lack of articles and research done on young adult identity formation during Covid-19, explanatory research is fundamental to this study. In addition to the research being exploratory, the research is also deductive in nature, which allows themes to emerge from the data itself (top down) and then identifying various codes and these using thematic analysis (Creswell et al., 2014). The study is also a cross-sectional study as it will be looking at information from a single fixed point in time. Cross-sectional study design will be used in this research as it is quicker to conduct and relatively inexpensive when compared to longitudinal studies which suit the scope of this research and its parameters (Creswell et al., 2014).

3.3. Population

3.3.1. Target population and population parameters

Du-Plooy Cilliers et al, defined population as a finite or infinite number of items that are in consideration for a specific study (2014). However, in each specific study there are criteria that must be met so that the study is researching individuals who meet the study's needs. Target population is a term used to describe and generalize the group of individuals whom the research will be based on (du-Plooy-Cilliers et al, 2014), this research will have the target population of young South African adults, who between the ages of 19-25 had experienced the lockdown and social distancing caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. Population parameters are the criteria such as the nature, size and characteristics of the population taking part in the study (duPlooy Cilliers et al, 2014). The population parameters within this research are a sample group size of eight willingly participants, who all meet the age requirement of being between the ages of 19-25 and had been in South Africa during the initial lockdown caused by Covid-19 in early 2020.

3.3.2. Accessible population

Accessible population is best described as the group of individuals that belong to the target population, are willing to participate in the research, meets the population

parameters and that the researcher would have convenient access too (du-Plooy Cilliers et al, 2014). An accessible population needs to be established as the research target population could include any individual who meets the criteria established but could stay in a location that is not easily accessible or may face challenges completing the interview. Therefore, the accessible population that this research will use are young South African adults, living in the Johannesburg area, who are willing to participate and must meet the population parameters of having to be age 19-25, and was undergoing their studies either in high school or university during the lockdown period of Covid-19 in 2020.

3.3.3. Unit of analysis

Units of analysis refers to the unit type that is determined based on the actual data analysis that is being performed in the study (Wellington & Szczerbinski, 2007). Units of observations refers to the unit or object that will be observed during the research. In this research the units of observations would be the individuals partaking in the study. The units of analysis for this research however would be the experiences of the individuals that were partaking in the research. However, for an individual to qualify for the research and be part of the units of analysis, one must also meet the requirements or parameters for research participants. These parameters would be ensuring that the participants are 19-25 years of age, is a university student and lived in South Africa during the lockdown of 2020.

3.4. Sampling

3.4.1. Probability or non-probability sampling

This research made use of non-probability sampling in order to conduct the research and gather findings from participants. Non-probability sampling was used as it would be impractical to reach the whole intended target population and the accessible population, so the researcher decided to use non-probability sampling in order to make use of their judgement to select a sample size of participants from the accessible population (Dudovskiy, 2016). Du-Plooy Cilliers et al (2014) states that non-probability sampling is a sampling technique that is about making sure that the

research has enough elements, elements being the participants in this research, in order to reach data saturation which means there is no new information being given throughout the data collection process. Non-probability sampling was chosen as it would be impractical to try and attempt to reach the full target and accessible population of which this research is based on. Limitations of non-probability sampling are due to the smaller number of participants there is a lack of representation of the target population, as well as a lower number of participants makes it more difficult to be able to generalize information amongst the participants (Dudovskiy, 2016).

3.4.2. Sampling method

In addition to non-probability sampling being used, the researcher also made use of convenience and purposive sampling methods. Convenience sampling is a form of sampling in which the sample is selected due to the convenience and availability of the sample to the researcher, purposive sampling is done when the researcher will purposefully include certain participants of the sample based on the researcher's judgement (du-Plooy Cilliers et al, 2014). Convenience sampling was used so that the research was able to search for participants which were most conveniently available, eight potential participants were found using convenience sampling and contacted via email if they were willing to be part of the research of which all eight agreed to comply. The researcher began the sampling process by reaching out to individuals he knew and he thought would be interested in participating in the research. Through a combination of email, social media and word of mouth, eight participants were found and selected to be possible participants.

Out of the eight who initially agreed to participate, there were two individuals who decided to drop out of participation in between the time of agreeing to participate and the final confirmation of the scheduled interview. One individual had to drop out due to conflicts in scheduling, unable to find a suitable time that worked the participant and the researcher. The second participant who dropped out simply claimed that they "didn't want to anymore", while an inconvenience this didn't too greatly affect the researcher as he had initially contacted eight participants to participate. So with two members dropping out, the researcher had to recontact

previous people and ask them to participate, this was a simple process as the participants who initially weren't chosen, were more than happy to comply and participate in the research. Information sheets were sent to all participants before they agreed to participate, so the participants would know what exactly the research comprised of (Edgar & Manz, 2017).

Purposive sampling was then used for the researcher to use his own judgement and select the five participants would be taken for the research (Dudovskiy, 2016). Out of the eight initial willing participants, only six had met the criteria for the study and had consented to the study. Five of them were selected using purposive sampling, these five were selected by the judgement and reasoning of the researcher. Out of the eight participants, five were part of the study, two of them were part of the study at a time but dropped out, and one was not chosen to participate.

Once the five participants were chosen, the researcher reached out again via email and social media to schedule in-person interviews at the participants house.

Conducting interviews at the participants home, or their choice of location, was decided to allow the participants to undergo the interview in an environment where they felt most comfortable. Interview questions were chosen and created to have a list of questions that would a good basis of information. Questions included asking about the nature of relationships and how relationships were affected due to lockdown.

3.4.3. Sample size

Using convenience and purposive sampling to conduct the study, resulted in the study having sample size of five participants. Using convenience and purposive sampling allowed the research to be more time and cost effective, as well due to the limitations of the study itself making it impossible to include the target population of the whole of South Africa. Thus, the sample size of 5 was chosen to meet the requirements and criteria within the study, while reaching data saturation that was stipulated for this research and bearing in mind the limitations of the research itself.

3.5. Data collection

3.5.1. Data collection method

In-depth interviews were used as the primary method of data collection. An in-depth interview is a “qualitative data collection method which allows you to pose questions to participants with the aim of learning more about their views, opinions and beliefs about a specific phenomenon”(du-Plooy Cilliers et al., 2014). In-depth interviews was chosen as it is often used to gather qualitative data and allows the researcher ask and elaborate on questions and answers, which helps understand the meaning of each participant’s answers (Howit & Cramer, 2017). Using in-depth interviews, answers given by the participants were able to be more rich and detailed, allowing for more information for interpretation and ensuring that answers given were elaborated upon making sure that the researcher would not be assuming information.

While in-depth interview were used within the research, the interviews were also set in a semi-structured way and followed a general interview approach, this means that the researcher is able to ask the questions needed but in an order that is more natural of a progression based on the way the participant is responding. General interview approach means that the interview will take form as a conversation, where standard but open-ended questions will be asked to obtain data (du-Plooy Cilliers et al. 2014). This method was chosen as it best suits the researcher and the research, being able to explain or elaborate anything the participant is unsure of, as well as allowing the researcher to probe for extra information were necessary. In-depth interviews were also chosen as the primary data collection because the research is based on the subjective experiences of Covid-19, and such experiences are better explored through conversation and dialogue. The disadvantage of using in-depth interviews, is the time-consuming process of conducting the interviews and following that the process of transcribing each interview (Howitt & Cramer, 2017).

Before the scheduling and conducting of interviews, the researcher created a set of semi-structured in-depth interview questions. Questions were created to ensure information about the subjective experience of everyone could be interpreted. Questions such as “How did lockdown affect your social relationships?” and “Were there any new roles you had to take due to lockdown?”, allowed for participants to give deep and meaningful answers about those subjective experiences. Questions were also directed at exploring how the participants have changed or viewed themselves different post lockdown, “Did Covid-19 and lockdown cause you to rethink the way you see yourself?”. Information sheets were also printed to allow participants to keep a copy of what the research was about, as well as including contact details for both the researcher and supervisor. Finally consent forms were drafted and printed so the participant could sign the consent form in person before starting the interviews.

3.5.2. Data collection application

Before any data collection for the research was conducted, the researcher applied for and gained ethical clearance to conduct research under the IIE. Emails were sent to the five chosen participants in the study confirming their selection and participation within the research, whereby after they agreed a date was scheduled at their convenience for an interview to take place. Consent forms for partaking in the research and consent to record had to signed and acknowledged by participants as the researcher planned to record the interviews for transcriptional a later date. All but one of the interviews were conducted at the participants homes. The one participant whose interview didn't take place at their own home, requested that the interview take place in a neutral location. The interviews were conducted at the participants home or location of choice. All interviews were conducted face-to-face. This was chosen as the participants would feel most comfortable undergoing interviews in their own space. This would also be the most convenient way to collect data, as the researcher could schedule interviews and drive to them at his own pace.

Prior to the start of the interview, the researcher asked the participants to sign a hard copy of the consent form and were given a hard copy of the information sheets to

keep. Interviews were conducted in locations where privacy could be ensured, and where the researcher could easily record the interview. The researcher used a recording device to record the whole interview, for later transcription at a later stage, but also used pen and paper to make small notes on certain things that were brought up. The interview following a semi-structured and general interview approach allowed the interview to flow as a conversation allowing both researcher and participant to feel more at ease, which led to more in-depth answers. Once interviews were concluded, the researcher took the consent forms and recorded interviews and transferred them to a secure folder on a password-protected laptop.

3.6. Data analysis

3.6.1. Data analysis method

Thematic data analysis was used to interpret the data, which is a method of analysis that consists of identifying, analysing and reporting repeated themes within qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Thematic analysis was used as it is one of the most utilised methods of analysing qualitative research (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). Another reason thematic data analysis was chosen is because it's a method that allows the researcher to identify and organise their own recognised themes that have emerged from the given dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2013). However, there is the limitation of thematic data analysis being difficult to implement properly.

The researcher used "Word" to transcribe each interview. This was time-consuming as the researcher could only remember and type a few words at a time. Since the interviews followed a general conversational interview approach the participants did tend to occasionally stray a little off topic which led to the transcriptions having answers from participants that were paragraphs worth of typing. This did allow the researcher however to become very familiarised with the data he collected and led to more ease when data analysis had to happen as there were already links and themes being identified during the early transcription stage of the research.

The transcribed interviews would be coded by grouping phrases and answers from the participants that had links between each other, from these linked codes the researcher would be able to identify and create themes. This method is known as the reflexive approach, which is building themes from the code (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Using thematic analysis also allowed the researcher to represent what the participants were saying in their own words. The researcher also utilised an inductive approach with the research, meaning that the data and the themes identified were strongly linked together.

The researcher utilised Braun & Clarke's six phases of thematic analysis to interpret the data. The first phase is familiarising yourself with the data, this is the step where the researcher will immerse themselves by reading the textual data several times (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Phase two is about analysing the data so that meaning can be generated between all participants. Phase three was the construction of themes from the data by searching for a meaningful pattern within the data (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Phase four is the review of the themes identified in the previous phase as well as a quality assurance to make sure the themes represent and is able to work with the dataset (Braun & Clarke, 2013). Phase four was accomplished with aid from the researcher's supervisor. Phase five is stating the significance of each identified theme (Braun & Clarke, 2013), this is done by ensuring that each theme is unique and while they must all link to each other, each theme must capture its own focus and must not be repetitive. The final phase is the write up of the report and provides a 'story' on the data based on the analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2013).

3.6.2. Data analysis application

The researcher conducted the interviews, collected data, transcribed the data and finally coded the data solely, this was done to allow the researcher ample opportunities to be immersed within the data and familiarise himself with the data. This is also the first phase of the six-phase approach to conduct thematic analysis as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2013). After the transcriptions were completed, the researcher was able to code the data which is the second phase of thematic

analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2013). This was done on paper and with highlighter, the researcher grouped together topics, ideas and thoughts that would be repeatedly brought up amongst the various participants. These grouped ideas and thoughts, hereby known as codes, would then be linked in order to create themes through the patterns that would repeatedly show up. These themes were elaborated upon and used as the basis for the thematic analysis and interpretation of the research.

For the thematic analysis to be completed, the researcher had to familiarise himself with the data. This was done by listening to, transcribing and reading each interview multiple times. Transcription was completed by the researcher playing the recording, pausing and typing what could be remembered. Once each transcription was completed the recordings would be sent to the researcher's laptop, where the transcriptions and the recordings could be securely stored, with access only available to the researcher and his supervisor. The recordings were then deleted from the recording device. From the transcribed interviews, the next step was to generate initial codes from the text, and from said code's themes had to be identified. This was done by printing out each transcript and while reading the text, the researcher highlighted different thoughts and ideas in each transcript while using a common colour amongst the transcriptions so identifying codes would be easier. From the different coloured coded codes, common ideas were linked together to create themes. The above described are the first three phases of Braun and Clarke's thematic data analysis (2013). Each of these three phases was used extensively and provided the guideline the researcher used in order to do the thematic analysis.

Phase four and five of Braun and Clarke's thematic data analysis are reviewing potential themes and, defining and naming of themes, respectively (2013). This was done by researcher linking common elements that would fit under an "umbrella" term encompassing all ideas into a theme. Phase four's purpose within thematic analysis is to review the themes and is a quality assurance to ensure that the themes identified are compatible with the dataset, while phase five's is stating the significance of each theme, ensuring that while all themes must all link together, each theme must also capture its own focus (Braun & Clarke, 2013). The themes were reviewed by the researcher's supervisor, the supervisor also helped with the

naming of themes. The five identified themes, just by name, were as follows:

(Theme

1) Role transition, (Theme 2) Relationships, (Theme 3) The virtual self, (Theme 4) Personal growth and (Theme 5) Interests. The last phase is the sixth phase, producing the report, which is the write up of the report and provide the “story” of the data based on interpretation and analysis.

The data that was collected and interpreted contained a lot of common feelings and thoughts about the experiences of living under lockdown during Covid-19. This helped with the formation of the themes as the themes were derived from the data itself under the reflexive approach (Baxter, 2017)

4. FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

4.1. Presentation of findings

Not all participants however shared the same views on the same topics, this allows the emergence of sub-themes within the themes. Sub-themes are also an example of how unique the human experience is, and while this research has had to generalise the ideas and emotions of a small population, it cannot be an accurate representation to fit the perspective and experiences of all individuals.

The themes that were identified from the codes within the transcript were created to encompass an aspect of what the experience of lockdown was and how it affected young adult identity. The themes are as follows (1) Role transition, (2) Relationships, (3) The virtual self, (4) Personal growth and (5) Interests. These themes were identified, and different codes grouped together as each theme represents an aspect of their lives which Covid-19, lockdown and social distancing all affected which would likely be a cause of a change or development in forming identity. The first theme of

“Role transition” was identified through the experiences of losing and gaining different roles as the lockdown period started and was extended. While most of the focus was on roles that were lost and gained at that time. There was also a focus from a few participants which spoke on how Covid-19 helped with the current roles they hold today. Role transition within households also impacted the participants relationships with friends and loved ones. Theme two, “Relationships”, explores the different ways people’s relationships were impacted due lockdown and social distancing caused by Covid-19.

Theme three of the “The virtual self” explores how people changed and adapted to the switch to an online world due to lockdown and social distancing. Aspects of life which would have completed outside or in social environments, were now forced to be experienced through a screen. Schooling, work and even the maintenance of relationships had to be attended to through the screen of a laptop or cell phone. The fourth theme of “Personal growth” encompasses thoughts, behaviours and changes in mindset that were a direct cause from the change in South African life caused on by Covid-19. Sub-themes will be implemented and will divide the growth theme into ‘growth’ and the second sub-theme will focus on how certain behaviours, thoughts or mindsets had regressed in anyway. The final theme identified in the research, is “Interests”, this theme speaks on activities, interests and hobbies that were either lost or gained throughout the lockdown period.

These themes and codes that made the themes are presented in Table 1 below.

<p>Theme 1: Role transition</p>	<p>I think it wasn't necessarily a case of like new roles being taken. But like, certain roles were kind of falling away.</p> <p>So, I kind of took on a sibling role</p> <p>I did help around a lot more with housework with my mom. I helped a lot with my sister's schoolwork a lot more because I was available.</p>
<p>Theme 2: Relationships</p>	<p>That made us a lot closer because we're spending a lot more time together.</p> <p>So relationships certain relationships like fell away or got weakened, and other ones kind of got stronger.</p> <p>So relationships with the opposite sex in terms of romantically, that almost became non-existent.</p> <p>I grew closer with my family, but in another we grew apart, I know that's very contradictory.</p>

	<p>All this like it went from a very social friendly kind of relationship to a just a formal.</p> <p>I think being in the same house and seeing each other's faces constantly throughout the day, I often became irritated and annoyed. And I felt that I didn't have my own space and privacy.</p>
<p>Theme 3: The Virtual self</p>	<p>I've thrived on the online learning system utterly thrived.</p> <p>But when lockdown happened, low and behold, I was a phone call person. Because you know</p> <p>And it became difficult to have online lectures and things. So a lot of our students have actually left to learn by ourselves through things like YouTube</p> <p>we didn't know each other and it was very difficult to communicate with each other because we didn't really know each other's personalities or actually know how each other looked. So it was very difficult to work with people.</p>

<p>Theme 4: Personal growth</p>	<p>Overall direction that I kind of got from lockdown like, it's made me crave more meaningful connections and time with people.</p> <p>It's made me more intune with quality time</p> <p>When I was more in their space. I found myself like regressing a lot more</p> <p>I don't want to say like, I became a less friendly person. But like, I still maintain those boundaries now like if I meet a new person</p> <p>So I just became a lot more like, selfconscious than anything else.</p> <p>In one word I'd say lockdown made me more mature</p> <p>The lockdown showed me how dependent I was on other people in terms of how help with my work and understanding work and it really forced me like I said to become more responsible with myself.</p> <p>So I'm definitely a lot more confident post lockdown.</p>
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	<p>So a lot of things I would have wanted to do before COVID happened I definitely don't want to do today.</p>
<p>Theme 5: Interests</p>	<p>I used to play like indoor in uni a bit. But like that was sporadic and then that had to stop.</p> <p>I will say it made me look at the activities that I lost, right made me realise I don't do meaningful things.</p> <p>Most of my hobbies are single hobbies that I do at home. So nothing changed there.</p>

Table 1. Themes and Codes

4.2. Interpretation of findings

The research problem and aim of this research is to explore how Covid-19, lockdown and social distancing affected how young adults see themselves and how it affected the development of their identity. While there were implications that were

had due to the Covid-19 virus being around, this research puts greater focus on how the social distancing and lockdown that were imposed due to Covid-19 affected the formation and development of young adult identity. Identity is defined as a fundamental organizing principal which develops constantly throughout the lifespan and is made up of the beliefs, experiences, memories, relationships and values which creates the individual's subjective sense of self, the identity (Erikson, 1950). In order to gain a deeper understanding of how identity could be developed or regressed during lockdown, the researcher used the participants subjective views on how the experience and memories of lockdown were and how their relationships and values were affected due to lockdown.

4.2.1. Theme 1: Role Transition

Theme one was labelled as "Role transition", participants went into great lengths to speak on how they lost certain roles that they were either accustomed too or getting used to. Participants one, four and five were all living either independently or with others, such as partners or roommates, and all mentioned losing certain roles of being either an "adult" or being an "independent being". This loss of independence was brought upon because all made decisions to move and stay with close or extended family during lockdown, and thus were no longer the eldest or in charge of their environment anymore but were now living with parents or guardians that the participants had to answer to. Participants four and five, both independent young adults, spoke of losing that sense of independence and taking on the role of a family member again, "So I kind of took on a sibling role", this is a direct quote from participant four describing how his role changed during lockdown, which he spent with his partner's family. Participants two and three, both lived with their parents before, during and after lockdown but also described how they lost their sense of freedom during lockdown.

Having set roles within an individual's life is important as roles that an individual associates themselves with, is a part of what forms identity (Erikson, 1950; Marcia, 1993). All participants had to take on new roles caused by the lockdown of Covid-19, while these roles were all varied, it was common amongst the participants that these roles were only taken out of necessity or obligation. These forced roles that were

taken on would have influenced the identity formation of the individuals at the time of the lockdown (Erikson, 1950; Marcia, 1993). However, when speaking post lockdown, when the participants were able to go back to the roles, they were either familiar with, or had wanted to pursue pre-lockdown, all participants spoke of how these new roles were enjoyed or what they envisioned for themselves. This probing how vital the roles we associate with ourselves with are to our identity.

4.2.2. Theme 2: Relationships

Theme two, “Relationships” was the most mixed response’s theme from the collected. All participants spoke on how certain relationships in their lives had improved due to lockdown. It was found that four of the participants all said that their relationship with their mother specifically grew stronger and closer during lockdown and that relationship is something that remains to this day. Participant four, the only one who mentioned a drift in relationship with their mother, was the only one who didn’t spend the lockdown with their mother as well. All participants also made mention of other relationships that were deteriorating. Some relationships, especially amongst other non-mentioned family members were put under the strain since family members were constantly around each other, “So it’s almost like everyone’s in each other’s business”, quote from participant two. This sort of tension that was displayed also contributed to the feelings of losing one’s freedom, through the loss of privacy. Teo has found in previous research that poor relationships are a major risk factor for developing depression (2013). While none of participants spoke of developing depression or experiencing depressive symptoms, there was a common agreement amongst the participants answers that being forced to engage with the same familial relationships everyday did cause strain on mental wellbeing.

Knez et al, has suggested that the more an individual identifies, emotionally and cognitively, with an environment the more an individual will experience wellbeing (2020). Participants one and four both left environments they considered home during the lockdown, being in a different environment that they weren’t identifying with left them with did lead to difficulties within everyday living as they were also essentially forced into having relationships everyday with people that they previously

didn't have much interaction with. Participants two, three and five stayed in their respective homes but tensions in certain relationships in their lives can lead to a disconnect from the environment. Relationships can shape an individual's selfconcept affecting one's identity, having strained relationships with family in forced conditions can lead to the maldevelopment of identity (Kwang, 2010).

Last aspect of relationships is how the relationship with the participants friends were affected. While all participants agree that the friendship and bond with some of their friends had been somewhat lost, it was how different participants dealt with such struggle which defined their relationships with friends then and today. A few of the participants accepted the conditions of lockdown, and only attempted rekindling friendships once the lockdown was completed. While two of the participants took the time to focus on relationships with their family members. Lastly participant one, utilised technology to a great degree and was able to not only maintain his friendships but build new ones during the lockdown period due to trying to connect with people whenever he could.

4.2.3. Theme 3: The Virtual Self

Theme three, "The Virtual self", the force to an online world and thus creating a virtual self was an expected response as this was the only way people could connect at such a time. All but one participant were university students at the time of lockdown, so the virtual self was created to comply with the change to online school. All studying participants agreed that while online lectures were an "easier" way of studying. While it became easier in some ways, as travel time was eliminated. It was also a method of school that allowed the participants to become more complacent by not having to truly "attend" the lecture.

Three of the four studying participants found it difficult to complete their assignments and lectures. This could be explained as online learning relies on the learner being able to make meaning through assuming agency in learning and maintaining meaningful online communications, as well as developing an understanding on engagement with digital resources (Chiu et al, 2021). With the participants not truly "attending" the lectures they are not engaging with the work or the lecturer.

Therefore, so many students have felt a negative impact on themselves and their academic careers due to online learning, it is the lack of connection to the lecturer and the content, as well as the lack of initiative and urgency which are often present in a classroom (Chiu et al, 2021). They missed and enjoyed the human connection of a classroom where lecturers and students would interact. Stress and anxiety due to the pandemic are other factors which could easily demotivate students, and negative emotions have been shown to inhibit learning (Chiu et al, 2021). Which was the case in majority of the participants, as not only was the online learning itself difficult for them but the lack of social interaction which includes opportunities to ask for help were missing as well. It has also been proven that social deprivation is linked with decreased levels of brain activity which could explain why so many of the participants struggled with online school during lockdown (Hein et al, 2020).

Participant three was the outlier who claimed that “I’ve thrived on the online learning system, utterly thrived.” This was the only case of who someone directly benefitted from the online school that lockdown brought on. With cases of individuals preferring the online learning system, it’s a matter of preference and opinion. Participant three was able to engage with the work and lecturers, despite being in an online setting. As well as maintaining levels of initiative and effort due to his own commitment to engage and understand the digital work though multimodal communication means (Chiu et al, 2021).

4.2.4. Theme 4: Personal Growth

Theme four was “Personal growth” and this theme must be split into two sub-themes being “personal growth” and “personal regression”. Personal regression is not as big as a change in the participants when compared to personal growth, but there are instances across the participants where their personalities, habits and mindsets had changed in ways that they viewed as negative growth or regression. Participant one speaks on how he feels as if he’s no longer as social as he used to be as he still “maintains those boundaries now like I meet a new person”, here he speaks of how

lockdown changes the way he approaches people and relationships and how it's still affecting him. Participant four adds on this idea and speaks how he was unable to express himself in the ways he once could. Both participants also expressed how these are changes that are still present at the time of the interview. Participant three claims that "Social and personal aspect is, has regressed" this was the case for participant three as he felt most of his social life, not including school life, and personal life such as self-care in a mental and physical capacity, had been neglected and he is still in a mindset that he doesn't need to care as much. All but one participant also to varying degrees say that their self-confidence dropped during lockdown due to lack of social activity and occasions to display or practice selfconfidence. This regression in certain aspects of identity formation could be explained by the fact that identity formation in adolescents is greatly influenced by the social environment (Orben et al, 2020). With the lack of the social aspect of their lives, identity is unable to develop to its fullest potential. One participant had her selfconfidence increased during lockdown as being around her family was her source of comfort and confidence.

Covid-19 and lockdown didn't only regress certain aspects of the individual development and mindsets of participants. There are a lot of discussion on how lockdown led to personal growth in positive ways. All participants took something positive away from lockdown and attributed gaining those skills or mindsets to the experiences that they had during lockdown. Participant one emphasized that during lockdown he became aware of how easy time and human connection could be lost. "It's made me crave more meaningful connections and time with people" and "it's made me more Intune with quality time", both these quotes display how lockdown changed the mindset of relationships and social activities within him. Participant two, had lockdown shown her how dependable she was on other people, be it for school or at home, and throughout lockdown worked on herself to improve herself physically, mentally and spiritually. Participant two quotes "It really forced me to become more responsible with myself".

Participants three, four and five all had personal growth in terms of their futures and careers. Participants three and four both pointed out that if it wasn't for the stresses

and uncertainty that lockdown brought upon people, they may have never be given the push needed to reach out and take the job. Participant three, who thrived on the online learning, was able to also work from home for the money he needed, and that freedom he got school and career wise has positively funnelled its way into his career today. Participant four on the other hand thanked lockdown, for opening is eyes to how precarious the job market was before and during lockdown. So instead of opting for a gap year after his honour's degree, he went straight to work out of a fear that he wouldn't get another job. But that job and decision has allowed him to provide for himself and gain back his independence. Participant five didn't need the lockdown to push or scare her into a career, but rather allowed her to spend the time she needed to find her passion and following the lockdown has switched her degree and is now completing a qualification in a field she is passionate for. The remaining participants who saw personal growth in their lives and identity fall into the theory that Marcia set out. Marcia had stated that individuals had to undergo a crisis in order to reach the last step of developing an identity (1993). Covid-19 and the social restrictions that were in place could be the crisis that certain young adults needed in order to reach identity formation. Lastly the four participants who told that their selfconfidence had gone down during lockdown, all also pointed out that following the end of lockdown and thus social activities were allowed again, self-confidence had increased and was on the increase.

4.2.5. Theme 5: Interests

The final theme was the theme of "Interests". Participants two and five, considered themselves introverts and both stated that most of their hobbies and free time spent would be spent on activities that could be enjoyed indoors and alone. Loss of interests was not a major effect on the said two participants. However, both did mention, social activities such as parties and going out with friends, as interests they did lose. The loss of these social activities would have negative impact on the development of identity. Erikson and Marcia states that identity formation is a stage of development which is greatly influenced by the social relationships and social environment that a young adult will be in (1950; 1993). By having these social activities being taken away, both the environment and the relationships are also

taken away from the individual, leaving an important stage of development stripped of factors that would influence it.

Participants one, three and four also made specific note of partying, going out and drinking with friends as social activities of interest that were lost as well. The above three participants however also made mention of the sport and physical exercise that could no longer be enjoyed due to lockdown. The loss of interest and hobbies such as soccer and golf, which was mentioned, would influence the development of identity in the future. As interest are motivating forces behind whether an individual carries out a task or not, and interests form part of a young adults developing self-identity which can help them connect with peers (Pellerone et al, 2015). Lack of sport for these participants not only affected physical and mental health, but also social relationships as they were relationships that were being built and maintained through these sports.

5. TRUSTWORTHINESS OF FINDINGS

In order for data to be accepted as trustworthy, a researcher must be able to display that the data analysis has been conducted in a concise and precise manner through recordings, be consistent throughout, and be able to systematize and disclose methods of analysis with sufficient detail that a reader is able to give credibility as well (Braun & Clarke, 2012). The researcher has adhered to these regulations by following the phases of thematic analysis as laid out by Braun and Clarke, these phases which were followed allows the reader to follow along with the process that the researcher took when interpreting the data (2012). Furthermore, all transcriptions and recordings were utilised greatly in order to understand the data, and the transcripts and recordings have been safely secured and stored in the event it is needed again.

6. CONCLUSION

6.1. Summary of findings as they relate to the research question, problem, hypotheses or objectives

The research set out to answer the question of how Covid-19 and the social disruptions affected young adult identity formation. Through the analysis and interpretation of data, it can be concluded that during the initial period of lockdown young adult identity formation was negatively affected. Young adults, at a stage in their lives where social environment plays a huge part in identity formation (Orben et al, 2020), being taken away hampered the ability for young adults to form identity, as so many aspects of their social, educational and family lives were being altered. That being said, just as Marcia states in his theory, crisis is needed for identity to be formed as individuals need a crisis to push themselves and explore different roles and opportunities (1993). All participants fit into the theory and stages that Marcia laid out, as all participants managed to come out of Covid-19 and lockdown with a stronger sense of identity. Whether that be through reinforced and changed behaviour and mindset, in a personal or professional capacity, and by utilising Covid-19 as a period where different opportunities were explored and stuck too, forming the identity of the individual to this day. All three objectives of the research were also met, firstly to see how lockdown and social distancing affected development of identity, which was mainly found to be negative or regressing points during initial lockdown but saw an improvement in identity formation post lockdown. Objective two, what were the experiences of the participants during the lockdown stage. Objective three, was to explore whether young adults felt that they managed to adequately achieve identity formation, which all participants seem to have been able to achieve identity formation.

6.2. Anticipated contribution of the study (Implications of findings)

Anticipated contributions that this research will provide to the field of psychology is insight into how young South African adults experienced the lockdown that Covid-19 brought about. While the researcher himself is a novice thus making the research not as credible as it could be, the researcher has provided research that can prove useful to future intended study of Covid-19 and identity formation. Not only is Covid-19 a newer pandemic which a lot of the affects that it brought are still unknown, the research is also set and bed in South Africa. Which has a lack of attention to and reach when it comes to the study and understanding or different psychological issues within South Africa.

6.3. Ethical considerations

6.3.1. Ethical considerations relating to participants

When dealing with ethical considerations regarding the participants of the study, the researcher had to consider the American Psychological Associations (APA) Ethics Principles and ensure that Principle A and Principle E were not broken under the APA Ethics and Principles. Principle A: Beneficence and non-maleficence, was ensured by the researcher understanding his position of power when dealing with sensitive information (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). The researcher ensured this by using the position only for research intentions and by avoiding harm to the participants, by ensuring they were not triggered during the interview process and that appropriate numbers were given for assistance to mental distress.

Principle E: Respect for people's rights and dignity, everyone individual has the right to privacy, confidentiality and self-determination, added to that psychologists and researchers must be aware of cultural differences based on age, race, gender etc and must ensure to avoid bias related to those differences (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). The researcher ensured this by being aware of any cultural differences or perspectives that the participant may have had, that were different to those of the researcher. As well as ensuring that all participants maintained anonymity and had their confidential information securely protected with access only available to the

researcher and supervisor. Thus respecting the privacy and confidentiality of the participants.

6.3.2. Ethical considerations relating to other stakeholders

Relating to other stakeholders, the researcher upholds Principle C: Integrity-accuracy, honesty and truthfulness; to Varsity College Sandton. Principle C: states that honesty is of great importance and that if there negative consequence are a result of deception, the researcher must do what can be done to mitigate these consequences (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). The researcher has adhered to this principle by remaining honest about the research being done and ensuring that all criteria set out by Varsity College Sandton and the IIE were maintained during the research process.

Ethical considerations regarding the researcher himself, most ethical issues that could pose a dilemma were taken care of early during the research process. The researcher had no issues obtaining ethical clearance and consent from participants of the study, both of which are needed for research to take place (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). While the point of research is to obtain answers, there is always an ethical dilemma of using deception within the results in order to get favourable results (Howitt & Cramer, 2017). The researcher has remained as impartial as possible and will present findings and data in a truthful manner, regardless of the outcomes of those answers.

6.4. Limitations of the study

Limitations of the study included the ability of the researcher himself. As a first time researcher, the interpretation while done to the best that the researcher could muster, will have flaws in it. As a lack of experience when conducting interviews could have affected the participants to not give the most honest answers. As well as the lack of experience when it comes to the interpretation, interpretation of data and people's subjective experience is a long process that requires experience in order to perform a more accurate interpretation (Braun & Clarke, 2012). The requirements and criteria of the research also stipulated that a maximum of 5 participants could

participate within a qualitative research project. While the 5 participants reached data saturation for this research project, it's important to note that 5 is too small of a sample size to represent all young South African adults.

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